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THE PROBLEM OF ENSURING THE RELIABILITY AND DURABILITY OF TURBOGASCOMPRESSORS (TGK) AT THE STAGES OF DESIGN AND PRODUCTION

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Abstract. *This article addresses the issue of increasing the service life of compressor stations with gas turbine engines by 2-3 times. The issue of extending the service life of aircraft gas turbine engines is particularly pressing due to their widespread use as drive units for gas pumping stations, particularly for offshore oil and gas field operations.*

Scientific and technological progress, which determines the creation of new compressor stations with increased productivity and efficiency, is based on the development of new ideas, the implementation of progressive technological processes, optimal design, increased cycle intensity, and the creation of new materials.

Solving the multifaceted challenges of improving efficiency and reliability requires the development of new, progressive reliability assurance methods. It must be recognized that reliability is built into the design, ensured in production, and confirmed and implemented in operation. Reliability science, like any science, should not merely state the state of affairs but rather illuminate, anticipate, and forecast the future [1, 2, 3].

Key words: *booster compressor station (BCS), technical resource, reliability of turbogas compressors (TGC), failure-free operation and durability indicators of turbogas compressors, structural strength*

INTRODUCTION

Improving the reliability and operational efficiency of oil and gas production equipment is a multifaceted task, requiring solutions to a wide range of theoretical and applied problems. These solutions require consideration of numerous factors that directly impact equipment performance, depending on regional, climatic, wellbore, and specific operating conditions (factors).

Key reliability assurance efforts encompass all stages of the development of a compressor station with turbogas compressors. During the design phase, over 700 computational programs in various fields are used to ensure the development of an optimal design. These programs include analysis of the design's performance and influencing factors, enabling early assessment and standardization of parameters, as well as determination of reliability indicators [4].

The design stage is crucial for ensuring reliability and service life, with the developer playing a key role. During the refinement process, quality and stability of production are ensured, and reliability requirements are established. At this stage, a system of specialized, long-term, and equivalent tests (more than 50 types) is implemented to confirm reliability. At the end of this stage, evaluation tests are conducted to refine and identify key parameters, validating the design data, calculation schemes, and theories [5, 6, 7].

For example, a gas turbine engine's combustion chamber has 16 parameters (reliability indicators) that must be confirmed during the development process. During the design process, a

redundancy, backup, and protection system, as well as a control and signaling system, are developed and implemented.

All failures, defects, and malfunctions discovered during the development of the TGC can be classified by various criteria, severity of consequences, manifestation, complexity of the phenomenon, and difficulty of elimination.

Of the total number of failures, more than 60% are strength-related, and up to 70% are vibration-related, which are associated with variable loads.

This is largely due to the lack of methods for assessing dynamic stresses at the design stage. The lack of scientific support also impacts failures related to thermal cycling strength, wear, and fretting corrosion.

Multicomponent loading conditions, irreversible changes in material properties, and instability of alternating loads are underutilized in forecasting. These issues require scientific investigation, and the role of industry standards in meeting practical needs in this area is still inadequate [8, 9, 10, 11].

The role of scientific reliability assurance is also insufficient for some issues of gas dynamics (self-oscillations, flow breakdown and non-uniformity, accuracy of calculation of blade profile characteristics, etc.), combustion processes (vibrational combustion, stability of radial and circumferential temperature distribution, assessment of boundary conditions, validity of modeling, etc., impossibility of predicting failures and malfunctions, underestimation of many factors with direct and feedback, etc.).

According to established mechanical engineering practice, the structural strength of components and assemblies is considered the basis for reliability. Structural strength includes design and strength calculations, material properties, manufacturing technology, and operating conditions. A mandatory component of structural strength is the scientific development of the problem. Structural strength is the strength under actual operating conditions, taking into account design, metallurgical, technological, and operational factors, which together determine the reliability of the TGC [12, 13].

Principles for ensuring high design reliability include the maximum possible use of scientifically based, generalized design experience, as well as our own experience in creating reliable engines and TGC drives. Testing of drives and other TGC operating components during development should be conducted under conditions as close as possible to operational conditions [14,15].

Work on eliminating defects is carried out under the assumption that each defect that appears has a specific, deterministic cause or set of causes, the likelihood of which should be reduced as much as possible.

The effectiveness of defect elimination measures is verified through calculations and comparative laboratory tests across a full range of operating conditions. Samples, models, and actual components are used. Engine serviceability reserves are assessed through specialized tests in a thermal and pressure chamber on a specially equipped rig.

A typical algorithm for qualification testing of the TGC:

- assessment of the vibration strength of the TGC, its components, and parts (self-oscillations, vibration stresses, critical speeds, torsional vibrations, etc.);
- temperature measurement (temperature fields, temperature of engine system elements, temperature of working parts, etc.);
- assessment of the functioning of subsystems (lubrication subsystem, starting and control subsystem, etc.);
- checking operational characteristics (stability of engine operation, quality of gas and air intake, etc.).

When designing long-life engines and ensuring their operational reliability, it is important to predict their remaining life and assess their current technical condition. The first stage of lifespan prediction is performed at the design stage using calculated stress parameters, the thermal state of

components, and the existing structural strength characteristics of materials. During refinement, the estimated lifespan of the TGC components is refined using measured alternating stresses and component temperature data.

The next stage of resource assessment involves studying the durability of actual components and parts and conducting equivalent engine tests for the specified service life. Both stages are preliminary and serve to assess the engine's service life capabilities.

Solar's approach to compressor design is focused on maximum simplicity and versatility. Solar compressors are designed to provide at least three years of continuous operation under load between two routine maintenance (inspections), and the main components are rated for 20 years of continuous operation.

Components and parts replaced during routine maintenance are typically limited to the installation of new babbitt sealing rings and bearings. Many of the components used in compressor designs comply with API 617.

Finite element analysis (FEA) software is used to determine stress levels in the main casing and its components. While the central section is designed to maintain tensile stress levels from centrifugal forces in accordance with ASME limits, the casing ends are made more robust to withstand separation forces, which relieve stress on the seals between the casing and end caps.

Special tools have been designed to facilitate maintenance during operation. For example, a complete compressor rebuild using tools for quickly removing the discharge end cover, the compressor rotor/stator assembly, installing the modified unit, and closing the end cover requires one eight-hour work shift.

Impellers range in size from 178mm to 665mm and are precision cast from stainless steel for strength and corrosion resistance (Fig. 1) [16].

Fig. 1. Compressor impeller

The impellers are designed for moderate stress levels and are suitable for use with sulphur dioxide (H₂S) in sulphide-containing environments (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Assembly of the compressor rotor type C-306 during installation and repair

All impellers undergo the following manufacturing processes:

- Heat treatment;
- Magnetic particle inspection;
- Visual inspection;
- Machining and balancing;
- Dimensional inspection;
- Maximum speed (115%) testing for 60 seconds;
- Liquid penetrant inspection using the fluorescence method.

Modern associated gas compression and transportation processes require high pressures (35-72 MPa) at pressure ratios reaching 30 and higher. These parameters can be achieved by sequentially operating compressors (typically two to four TGCs). Therefore, it is important to have a set of TGCs that can relatively easily achieve the required parameters for both maximum volume and pressure of the compressed gas. Experience in global compressor engineering shows that such mobility is possible if TGCs are designed using standardized basic components and assemblies.

CONCLUSION

To ensure engine reliability and implement condition-based maintenance, methods for assessing and predicting the life of the TCG are crucial.

For this purpose, methods for assessing the technical condition of the TCG, ensuring its maintainability, are used. All monitoring methods must be implemented at the compressor station, covering all systems and components.

The current technical condition is assessed using the integrated automatic monitoring and alarm system, the results of data processing of measured parameters, and the dynamics of their change over time.

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